

DETERMINATION OF INTERFACE MODULUS BY ULTRAMICROINDENTATION TECHNIQUE IN Al_2O_3 PARTICULATE REINFORCED 6061 Al METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Ultramicroindentation studies have been performed on both for a 15%, irregular shape, Al_2O_3 p-6061 and a 20%, spherical shape Al_2O_3 p-6061 metal matrix composites. From these studies, it appears possible to ascertain the mechanical properties of the interface region in terms of modulus of elasticity. It is found that the modulus of the interface is influenced by thermal ageing time at a constant ageing temperature.

INTRODUCTION

The macroscopic mechanical properties of particulate metal matrix composites (MMC) are controlled by those of the matrix, the particulate phase and also the interface region. Whilst the properties of the matrix and the particulate phase are not difficult to determine, it is often the interface region that poses difficulties. Chemical interaction between matrix and reinforcement may lead to discrete phases at the interface. Furthermore, the matrix region adjacent to the particles may show higher dislocation densities compared with the matrix due to mismatch of the coefficient of thermal expansion between the matrix and the reinforcement [1]. This may lead to enhanced matrix precipitation in age-hardenable aluminium alloys.

Microindentation techniques have recently been developed that employ indentation loads of the order of milli-newton (mN), thereby resulting in depths of microindentation that are of the order of nano-meters (nm). Such systems give high spatial resolution in hardness as well as elastic modulus [2]. Such a system is considered to be well suited to the study of particle-matrix interfaces in composite materials. In the present work, a series of indentations were performed to measure the hardness profile and elastic modulus across the particle/matrix interface in the two Al_2O_3 -Al composites.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

2.1 Materials

The materials used in this experiment were a) 15% Vf Al_2O_3 /6061 (angular Al_2O_3 particles) and b) 20% Vf Al_2O_3 /6061, Comral 85 (spherical Al_2O_3 particles). The optical microstructures of the composites are given in figures 1 and 2, and the details of the production method are given elsewhere [1].

Figure 1: Optical micrograph of 15% Vf Al_2O_3 (angular) - 6061 Al. Scale Bar = 40 μm .

Figure 2: Optical micrograph of 20% Vf (spherical) Al_2O_3 -6061Al. Scale Bar = 40 μm .

Both materials were solution treated at $530^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours in a vertical tube furnace then quenched in cold water at 0°C . Subsequently, the specimens were artificially aged at $175^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 2, 8 and 72 hours. Ageing at this temperature for 8 hours represents the T6 condition. This means ageing for 2 hours represented under-ageing whilst that for 72 hours created over-aged specimens.

2.2 The Ultramicroindentation System

The mechanical properties of the matrix, interface and the particulates were investigated using a UMIS-2000 ultra low-load indentation system. Details of the specification and operation of this equipment are given elsewhere [2]. In this system, the depth of penetration of an indenter tip as a function of the applied indenting force is measured – the independent resolutions of indentation depth and force being 1 nm and 0.01 mN respectively. The indenter was a Berkovich diamond pyramid with a nominal angle of 65.3° between the tip axis and the faces of the triangular pyramid. Measurements were first made by increasing the loading force in steps to a predetermined maximum of 30 mN, then decreasing the loading force, by the same step-sizes, to zero load. A typical load displacement diagram during loading and unloading is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: A schematic load-unload curve for a material when indented with a Berkovich indenter. This figure illustrates the elastic, plastic and residual components of the total penetration of an indenter into the surface.

Load-displacement data were acquired at pre-selected sites, or arrays of points, across a surface from the matrix through the "interface" into the reinforcing particles. [Also, to obtain chemical mapping across the particle-interface-matrix, an electron-probe-micro-analyser technique was used. However these results and their correlation with the ultramicroindentation studies will be published elsewhere [3].]

2.3 Determination of the Elastic Modulus

The elastic modulus of the specimens (E) can be determined as follows [2]:

$$E/(1-\nu^2) = E^*E/[E_i - E^*(1-\nu_i^2)] \quad (1) \quad \text{and}$$

$$\frac{dp}{dh} = \alpha E^* A^{0.5} \quad (2)$$

where E and ν are the Young's modulus and poisson's ratio of the specimen, E^* the effective modulus of the system, E_i and ν_i are the modulus and Poisson's ratio of the indenter diamond p the force applied, h the depth of plastic penetration, α a constant ($=1.167$), and A is the projected area of contact. Experimentally, $E_i = 1050$ GPa and $\nu_i = 0.3$. Further, for metallic materials $1-\nu^2 \approx 1$. Therefore, $E/(1-\nu^2) \approx E$ *i.e.* modulus of the specimen. Several tests were performed on each sample and an average was then taken.

For materials with a high ratio of hardness to modulus, a curvature is obtained in the unloading force-displacement curve (figure 3), due to elastic recovery. However, a linear behaviour is found in the initial stage of the unloading portion of the force-displacement curve, and E^* is usually determined by a linear fit to the initial few points in the unloading curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In figure 4 are shown the loading-unloading curves for the two composites in the T-6 ageing condition. Three different sets of curves are obtained corresponding to (a) matrix, (b) interface, and (c) particles. Figure 5 shows the average curves obtained from figure 4 for the three different regions. The indentation for the particle is the smallest, as expected, and that for the matrix is the largest, the interface region showing intermediate behaviour.

In Table 1 are presented the summary of findings related to the hardness of the specimens as obtained from figures 4 and 5. It can be seen that maximum hardness occurs for the matrix at the peak ageing condition (T6) *i.e.* at 8 hours. It is also noticed that the interface hardness follows the same pattern indicating that its properties are related to both the microstructural conditions and the stiffness properties of the matrix. The hardness of the particles are higher than both the matrix and the interface but show a significant scatter, presumably due to the varied proximity of the particles to the indenter tip, or due to varied degree of compactness of the particles.

The elastic moduli of the matrix, interface and the particulate phase are given in Table 2. Leaving the particulate phase aside, which again represents scatter in measurement, *it is clear that one can assign a quantitative value to the modulus of the interface region (that between the modulus for the matrix and the particle.)* Again the variation of the interface modulus is in agreement with the variation of the matrix property, as induced by the ageing treatments. Since variations in the modulus of the matrix with ageing time are associated with precipitation effects in these age-hardenable materials, it is likely that the variations in elastic modulus are related to microstructural changes associated with precipitation hardening. The thickness aspect of this interface region will be discussed in another paper [3].

Figure 4: Force-penetration plots for the particulate phase, interface and matrix; 8 hours ageing (a) 15% Al_2O_3 MMC (b) 20% Al_2O_3 (spherical) MMC.

Figure 5: Average force-penetration plots for the particulate phase, interface and matrix; 8 hours ageing (a) 15% Al₂O₃-MMC, (b) 20% Al₂O₃ (spherical)-MMC.

Table 1: The maximum depth of indentation for the matrix, interface and the particles and corresponding hardness values for these three regions (average values).

Materials	Ageing Time (Hrs)	Depth of Indentation [nm] (Hardness at Maximum Depth [GPa])		
		Matrix	Interface	Particle
15% Al ₂ O ₃	2	897.62 (1.59)	664.0 (3.18)	290.12 (20.9)
	8	725.4 (2.45)	521.15 (5.10)	288.5 (21.5)
	72	879.62 (1.64)	542.86 (4.68)	313.61 (18.7)
COMRAL-85	2	931.58 (1.44)	634.09 (3.21)	331.85 (15.6)
	8	762.80 (2.16)	511.8 (5.41)	286.0 (22.6)
	72	865.28 (1.72)	621.7 (3.48)	309.44 (20.3)

Table 2: The value of $E/(1-\nu^2)$ for the matrix, interface and the particles in composites.

Materials	Ageing Time (Hrs)	$E/(1-\nu^2) \approx E$ [GPa]		
		Matrix	Interface	Particle
15% Al ₂ O ₃	2	68.7	80.4	215.8
	8	95.1	116.2	181.9
	72	74.8	102.2	240.5
COMRAL-85	2	68.9	95.2	175.0
	8	91.5	110.6	175.7
	72	78.4	107.6	236.4

CONCLUSIONS

By using the ultramicroindentation technique, it was seen that 1) there is clearly a region existing between the matrix and the particle, 2) this interface has a distinct and "measurable" elastic modulus. The magnitude of this modulus is in between that of the matrix and the particle, but closer to the modulus of the matrix. 3) The modulus of the interface has a direct dependence on that of the matrix.

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REFERENCES

1. T. Das, P.R. Munroe, and S. Bandyopadhyay, "The Effects of Al_2O_3 Particulates on the Precipitation Behaviour of 6061 Al-Matrix Composites", **J. Materials Science**, submitted for publication.
2. T.J. Bell, A. Bendeli, J.S. Field, M.V. Swain, and E.G. Thawite, "Determination of Surface Plastic and Elastic Properties by Ultramicroindentation", **Metrologia**, 28, 1991-92, p463-469.
3. T. Das, P.R. Munroe, S. Bandyopadhyay, T.J. Bell, and M.V. Swain, "Correlation Between EPMA and Ultramicroindentation Studies of Interfaces in Al_2O_3 -Al-Matrix Composites", to be published.